

Achieving openness - In global collaboration

Mogens Sandfaer*

*mosa@dtu.dk

0000-0001-8436-5346

National Open Research Analytics, Technical University of Denmark, Denmark

1. Abstract

Open research information and systems are required to enable research discovery and research analytics with high integrity, transparency and reusability. However, the switch to openness for such infrastructures is often a challenge, as the legacy of closed data and systems still dominates the area and the skillsets of many actors and experts. At the same time, the data of such open systems must live up to the highest standards of quality, precision and consistency to provide meaningful and useful open research information and analytics.

In Denmark, over the last few years, consistent efforts have been invested in achieving such openness, integrity, transparency and reusability. All along, this has been a project with deep and wide-spread collaboration with partners all over the world. The background, visions, approaches, partnerships, achievements, and challenges of the effort to open the Research Portal Denmark are explained.

2. Background and purpose

[Research Portal Denmark](#) is a national research information and analytics infrastructure and portal. It is developed and run for the Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science by National Open Research Analytics, the NORA team at the Technical University of Denmark. It is based on data and expertise from institutional, national and global domains – collected, aligned, and interlinked in the infrastructure and the Open Access portal. The scope of coverage is Danish research inputs and outputs since 2011 - when the Danish research landscape was thoroughly reorganized.

When it comes to information types, the vision is to cover as many as required to thoroughly cover the input, output and impact of Danish research. The types with green background indicate the starting points – where data sources are available and priority is high.

In parallel, it is a high priority to keep the data infrastructure as open as possible with the widest possible potential for reuse by the stakeholders of the Danish research landscape and interested parties elsewhere.

In a wider context, the portal is part of a Danish answer to the question: How to adapt to and benefit from the emerging landscape of responsible analytics and assessment, Open Science developments, the shift towards Open Research Information – as well as the increasingly PID-enabled internet of science and research?

More than 10 years ago, the [Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics](#) and the [Declaration on Research Assessment](#) introduced a much needed critical review of the quantitative research assessment approaches that had become routine in many countries - and proposed new principles for the measurement of research performance. In parallel, the [European Union](#) gradually increased the Open Science ambitions and requirements in its Horizon research funding programmes – and increasingly put Open Science at the centre of its research policy and planning. The [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), supported by 194 countries, took this to the global level. While all these principles and recommendations of the last 10

years fit quite well together, the open datasets and infrastructures that are required to implement such ‘better measurement of research performance’, etc. in practice have been a much slower development.

However, with the recent developments towards [Open Research Information](#), the launch of [OpenAlex](#) and the [CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition](#), new opportunities have arisen to turn theory into practice. The approach taken by Research Portal Denmark draws on these open global developments - as well as Danish research institutions, funders, and infrastructures, and – potentially – a supplementary data input from a commercial provider.

3. Starting point and preparations

Before starting the current 2025-project to open and consolidate the Portal, it was primarily a collection of publication services developed in parallel over the previous years and then brought together in a combined user interface/portal and interlinked as far as possible. The two key services:

- ‘Search Local Data’ - Data gathered from the local CRIS systems of 20+ Danish research institutions made available in a single deduplicated and merged database. In technical terms this constitutes a national CRIS index and is the oldest component of the Portal.
- ‘Search Global Data’ - Data pertaining to Denmark gathered from the 3 commercial global data providers Clarivate, Elsevier, and Digital Science made available one by one in each their database and – in addition – in a cross-search service offering single search across all three but with limitations wrt. metadata display and reuse imposed by the contracts with the commercial data providers.

While these services substantially simplify working across the 25+ databases, aggregated in the Portal, the approach did not fully deliver on the warmest wish of the [Ministry and the Advisory Board](#): *One consolidated publication database and a single publication search – with free reuse of the metadata.*

Consequently, studies and experiments were carried out in 2024 to prepare for the implementation project in 2025. Most notably:

The Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University was commissioned to perform an in-depth review of the portal’s technical infrastructure with recommendations for future improvements. The report ‘[CWTS review of Research Portal Denmark: Technical infrastructure](#)’ was finalized and made available on the Portal’s web-site in November 2024. The key CWTS recommendation was to implement a new common data workflow/data pipeline system to replace the existing technologies developed case-by-case over the previous years. The proposed data workflow was inspired by the [Medallion Architecture](#), with the aim to make the workflow more robust, easier to maintain, less complex, and faster to execute. Consequently, this became the major 2025 IT-development project for the portal backend.

To pursue the quest for open metadata, several experiments with [OpenAlex](#) data were carried out in 2024. The Portal became an OpenAlex Premium user, tested the various data acquisition alternatives, build internal prototypes to understand the issues involved in integrating such a new data source. The OpenAlex coverage of Danish research was compared in detail with the Portal’s existing data sources and published on the web-site in the

report ‘[Coverage of Danish Research Publications: Local and Global Data Sources of Research Portal Denmark](#)’, reflecting the status of late 2024.

For the Portal to enable research analytics with high quality and integrity, well-calculated and well-respected indicators would be needed. In most cases, the calculation of such indicators requires the entire global dataset to be downloaded, while the Portal only downloads and processes the subset of data pertaining to Denmark. Similarly, in many cases benchmark figures for comparing aspects of Danish research with other countries and regions would be needed. In dialogue with CWTS a solution was found utilizing their global infrastructure behind the [CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition](#). A service agreement was set up, ready to be tested during the 2025-project.

4. Implementation, data and methods

This section gives a step-by-step high-level overview of the 2025 implementation project for publication metadata - well underway but not yet finished. The Portal’s new ‘medallion-style’ data workflow/data pipeline system is being developed, tested and improved as a key part of the project.

(A) Danish research institutions

Danish research institutions document their research output in so called CRIS-systems¹. Researchers and librarians collaborate to achieve good coverage and compliance with the national Open Access policy. A national exchange format (XML schema) for this kind of metadata has been in place for many years. The metadata is made available for harvesting by the Portal using this format and the OAI-PMH data exchange protocol.

¹ Current Research Information System

(B) Danish CRIS index

This component of the Research Portal Denmark (RPD) infrastructure harvests the institutional CRIS'es. The aggregated data is cleaned, normalized, enhanced, matched and clustered – and finally merged to produce the best possible one-publication-one-record index of the institutional data contributions. The Danish CRIS index makes its data freely available for downloading by others – and this is practiced by national as well as international entities.

(C) OpenAlex indexing

OpenAlex downloads the data of the Danish CRIS index and integrates it in its global and open aggregation of research outputs (works). The OpenAlex aggregation includes data from many open collections like ArXiv, PubMed, HAL, etc., etc. – and data from the global PID-services Crossref, DataCite, ROR and ORCID. As indicated on the diagram, Denmark also interacts and contributes directly to these PID-services via national consortiums for DataCite and ORCID membership – while Danish funders and grants are starting to join the Crossref Grant Linking System - and a dialog with ROR has started to explore whether RPD could/should assume a role as the Danish national ROR curation partner.

With the many data sources of OpenAlex this submits the Danish records to global level cleaning, normalizing, enhancing, matching, clustering and merging procedures. This results in numerous data enhancements like adding the fine-grained Leiden-style topics to identify subject areas. This again is used to add OECD Fields of Research and Development classification codes (FORD) to the records, which is a special requirement of the Ministry and Statistics Denmark.

Firstly, this contributes to a good coverage of Danish research in an open global database of growing importance – a database that also underpins important services such as the CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition. Secondly, these enhancements make the data valuable for RPD to harvest back and integrate and enrich its own database of Danish research outputs. This is done by downloading the monthly snapshots from OpenAlex and submitting the in-scope part of the data to the RPD ingest pipeline – once again involving cleaning, normalizing, enhancing, matching, clustering and merging.

(D) Adding CWTS Leiden indicators

High-integrity indicators known from the CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition are received from CWTS twice per year based on a list of in-scope OpenAlex works-ID supplied by RPD. In addition, CWTS delivers publication-level classifications of the subtopics defined in the Danish Green Research Strategy of the Ministry of Higher Education and Science. This enables RPD to offer these as search criteria as well as to build analytical modules and dashboards that monitor research and innovation in connection with the green transition in Denmark. Finally, CWTS delivers global baseline and benchmark data for such analytical modules – as RPD only aggregates and indexes works-level data for Danish affiliated works.

(E) Adding data from step B-D to Research Portal Denmark infrastructure

The open data from the Danish CRIS index, OpenAlex and CWTS are all submitted to the RPD ingest pipeline and stored in the database infrastructure

(F) Adding licensed data to Research Portal Denmark infrastructure

In addition to the open data sources, RPD is in dialog with the current commercial providers to establish whether one or more of these would like provide data to the new open portal. This

would be of value to Danish users very accustomed to use and interpret the commercial databases. In case, the licensed data will also be submitted to the new RPD ingest pipeline involving cleaning, normalizing, enhancing, matching, clustering and merging.

(G) Notifying Danish research institutions

Based on this wide-area aggregation and integration of data on Danish research, RPD has knowledge of works/publications that one or more sources consider as affiliated to a Danish institution, which we did not find in the data coming from that institution itself. This enables RPD to notify the institutions about these potentially missing publications in their CRIS'es. Based on this, the institutions may choose to add the publication to their local system – copying data from the open part of RPD or drawing on their own commercial license agreements as they wish.

(H) Search and analytics services of Research Portal Denmark

As already touched upon RPD offers a range of search services – currently for publications, patents, and grants with more to come – and a beginning range of analytical services – starting with module on Danish green research with many more to come. Whenever publication data is part of such an analytical service it benefits from the international collaboration described above.

5. Status and challenges

The Portal's new 'medallion-style' data workflow/data pipeline system exists in a prototype version being tested to ingest and process the data from the Danish CRIS Index (B), OpenAlex (C), and CWTS (D). It is a work in good progress with continuous improvements, most likely ready as a version 1 by the end of 2025. - All Research Portal Denmark software is open source and equipped with open documentation.

The OpenAlex indexing of the Danish CRIS data (C) just started this Summer, as OpenAlex itself is engaged in full rewrite of its data workflow/data pipeline system. This means that it is not yet fully understood to what extent the data exchange with OpenAlex will require changes in the Portal's automated and manual processes.

Looking ahead, it would be interesting to explore if and how the [OpenAIRE](#) infrastructure could play a similar role as OpenAlex in this setup. Having two complementary global players index the Danish CRIS data and provide each their enhancements and supplements to the Danish Portal infrastructure seems valuable.

It remains to be seen whether data from one or more of the commercial data providers (F) will become available. In case, this will require extra effort towards the end of the year.

One challenge to be addressed in the Fall has appeared around the synchronization of updates from OpenAlex and CWTS. Currently, the Portal updates its OpenAlex data monthly and the CWTS data twice per year. This opens for potential confusion in the user interface of analytical modules using the CWTS data intensely. As a measure of analytical transparency, search links are provided which will take the user from an element in a dashboard to the corresponding search result in the search module so the user may inspect and further analyse the underlying publications. With the substantial difference in update frequency, the counts in the search module will often differ from those in the analytical module. Could a 'compromise' solution be for RPD and CWTS to move to quarterly updates of OpenAlex data, followed by the supply of CWTS indicator data to RPD?

6. Next steps

After the launch of the Open Research Portal Denmark with its fully refreshed backend system, procedures and infrastructures, resources need to be allocated to ‘polishing’ and optimizing the system. There is also an appetite to start a similar full refresh of the Portal’s front-end systems, responsible for the website with its search and analytics services. Beyond that, recent developments seem to point to a very interesting opportunity around open grant information – with a high degree of reuse of the systems developed and experience gained building the Portal’s open publication information service.

Firstly, the Portal and its [Working Group for Funders and Grants](#) have established a Danish Grants Index following the same pattern as the Danish CRIS Index: Defining a national metadata exchange format, aggregating data exported from the individual funders grant management systems, and building a consolidated database or index with search and export services.

Secondly, this Summer [Welcome announced](#) a substantial grant over three years ‘to support the indexing of grants from the world’s research funders into the OpenAlex database ... and help it provide links between grants and scientific works to support impact monitoring’.

Together this seems to open the door for grants to benefit from the same kind of local→national→global→and back collaboration as was developed for publications.

(A) Danish research funders

Supplying their grant metadata in the national exchange format

(B) Danish Grants Index

A consolidated national index with search and export services.

(C) OpenAlex Index

OpenAlex downloads the data of the Danish Grants Index and integrates it in its global and open aggregation with substantial enhancements – for example by adding more links between grants and publications.

(D) Grant Indicators?

It remains to be seen, whether high-integrity funding indicators will be produced by the OpenAlex/Welcome project or whether third parties like CWTS Leiden will add such to their portfolio of services.

(E) Adding data from step B-D to Research Portal Denmark infrastructure

(F) Adding European data to Research Portal Denmark infrastructure

Many Danish research projects are funded by EU grants. These grants and projects are well documented in the open [CORDIS database](#). Extracting the Danish affiliated grants and projects and adding these to the RPD data would complement the grants from Danish funders and increase the RPD coverage substantially.

(G) Notifying Danish research funders

The preceding steps will disclose information about grants from Danish funders, which was not reflected in their original metadata supply – such as links between grants and resulting publications. The Portal can identify these and report them to the funders that may choose to update their local grant management systems accordingly.

(H) Search and analytics services of Research Portal Denmark

This could be a logical and rewarding next step for the Research Portal Denmark.

7. Conclusions

This presentation describes how Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science, the Danish research institutions, the Danish research funders, Statistics Denmark and the NORA team collaborate to build a high-quality national research information infrastructure and portal.

While remaining a fully nationally based and controlled infrastructure, the necessary data quality and coverage is based on extensive collaboration and data exchange with global open infrastructures such as the PID registries and databases, a free and open database of scientific works such as OpenAlex, and high-integrity indicators from the CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition. All in the spirit of digital sovereignty, responsible research assessment, and the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#).

Research Portal Denmark chose to couple this collaboration and data expansion with a full rewrite of its backend system. This will future proof portal and enable even wider collaboration and data expansion in the coming years.

The combined results of these efforts and this national and global collaboration should be ready to inspect, use and reuse by early 2026 – as a Danish contribution to the growing landscape of Open Research Information infrastructures.

8. Open Science practices

All Research Portal Denmark user services are freely and openly accessible to anyone on the web. By the end of 2025, all data will be freely and openly available for download and reuse by anyone. All code and software are Open Source and will, by the end of 2025, be freely and openly available for download and reuse by anyone – in documented form.

The current data and software enable services that will support an initial set of Open Science analytics and assessment. However, a much wider set of data is required to fully enable Open Science assessment.

As indicated by the illustration from section 2 above, there are many aspects of research, its practice, results and impact that still need to be documented and added to the portal.

With the new backend system fully in place next year, the portal should be ready to start filling these gaps.

And, very recently, the international Open Science Monitoring Initiative released its [Principles of Open Science Monitoring](#), which may guide the development of Open Science analytics.

9. Funding information, competing interests, and acknowledgements

All the work and investments described are fully funded by the [Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science](#).

The author has no competing interests.

The author would like to thank for the hard and inspired work delivered by the current [NORA Team & Partners](#) and the NORA Team Alumni: Karen Hytteballe Ibanez (0000-0002-8229-0392), Søren Willer Hansen, Nikoline Dohm Lauridsen (0000-0002-6139-0108), Ivar Ternsell Torgersen, and Dicte Madsen (0000-0003-4746-4235).

The author would like to thank our key collaborators at CWTS: Nees Jan van Eck (0000-0001-8448-4521), Bram van den Boomen (0009-0005-5127-1200), André Brasil, and Ludo Waltman (0000-0001-8249-1752)

The author would like to thank our key collaborators at OpenAlex/OurResearch: Kyle Demes (0000-0003-2780-0393), Steve Gruber, and Jason Priem (0000-0001-6187-6610)

The author would like to thank colleagues at these related and like-minded national projects for inspiration, sparring and sharing: France: [French Open Science Monitor](#), Portugal: [PTCRIS](#) and related infrastructures, Finland: [Research.fi](#).